

DESIGNING APPROPRIATE ACTIVITIES FOR TEACHING SPEAKING TO YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation : First of all, to provide information about the types of methods that work on the development of speaking skills, to demonstrate how to use modern technologies in the educational process, to analyze new types of exercises according to the text, and most importantly, to Information is given on what difficulties students face in the process of speaking and how to prevent them.

Techniques should cover the spectrum of learner needs, from language-based focus on accuracy to message-based focus on interaction, meaning, and fluency.

When you do a jigsaw group technique, play a game, or discuss solutions to the environmental crisis, make sure that your tasks include techniques designed to help students to perceive and use the building blocks of language. At the same time, don't bore your students with lifeless, repetitious drills. The drills must be as meaningful as possible.

2. Techniques should be intrinsically motivating.

Try at all times to appeal to students' ultimate goals and interests, to their need for knowledge, for achieving competence, autonomy, and for "being all that they can be." Even in those techniques help them to see how the activity will benefit them.

Many times students don't know why we ask them to do certain activities. So techniques should encourage the use of authentic language in meaningful contexts.

It is not easy to keep coming up with meaningful interaction. It takes energy and creativity to devise authentic contexts and meaningful interaction, but with the help of quite a storehouse of teacher resource material now it can be done. Even drills can be structured to provide a sense of authenticity.

4. Provide appropriate feedback and correction.

In most EFL situations, students are totally dependent on the teacher for useful linguistic feedback. It is important that you take advantage of your

knowledge of English to inject the kinds of corrective feedback that are appropriate for the moment.

5. Capitalize on the natural link between speaking and listening.

Many interactive techniques that involve speaking will also of course include listening. Don't lose out on opportunities to integrate these two skills. As you are perhaps focusing on speaking goals, listening goals may naturally coincide, and the two skills can reinforce each other. Skills in producing language are often initiated through comprehension.

6. Give students opportunities to initiate oral communication.

A good deal of typical classroom interaction is characterized by teacher initiation of language. We ask questions, give directions, provide information, and students have been conditioned only to "speak when spoken to." Part of oral communication competence is the ability to initiate conversations, to nominate topics, to ask questions, to control conversations, and to change the subject. As you design and use speaking techniques, ask yourself if you have allowed students to initiate language.

7. Encourage the development of speaking strategies.

The concept of strategic competence is one that language students must be aware of. They simply have not thought about developing their own personal strategies for accomplishing oral communicative purposes. Your classroom can be one in which students become aware of, and have a chance to practice such strategies as:

- asking for clarification (What?)
- asking someone to repeat something (Huh? Excuse me?)
- using fillers (Uh, I mean, Well) in order to gain time to process
- using conversation maintenance cues (Uh huh, Right, Yeah, Okay, Hm)
- getting someone's attention (Hey, Say, So)
- using paraphrases for structures one can't produce

Types of Classroom Speaking Performance

With the obvious connection between listening and speaking, six categories of oral performance are expected to carry out in the classroom.

Imitation of this kind is carried out not for the purpose of meaningful interaction, but for focusing on some particular element of language form.

A question that new teachers in the field always want to have answered is: Is drilling a legitimate part of the communicative language classroom? The answer is a qualified "Yes". Drills offer students an opportunity to listen and

orally repeat certain strings of language that may pose some linguistic difficulty either phonological or grammatical.

Intensive speaking is designed to practice some phonological or grammatical aspect of language. Intensive speaking can be self-initiated or it can even form part of some pair work activity, where learners are "going over" certain forms of language

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